

O'zDS† ISO \ IEC 17021:2009 REQUIREMENTS FOR INFORMATION RESOURCES AND THE WORK PROCESS OF THE CERTIFICATION BODY

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The presentation of information requirements in the standard is the result of a compromise balancing between the principles of openness and confidentiality. Openness implies, first of all, public access to information about the activities of the certification body, which must update and make publicly available (or provide upon request) information about audit and certification processes, types of management systems, etc.

From Guidelines 62 and 66, the standard retained the provision on the public nature of the list of certified clients to whom the certification body issues certification documents (which it decides). At the same time, unlike the requirements of Guidelines 62 and 66, the content of these documents should be somewhat adjusted and clarified.

So, they should contain the following additional information:

- an expiration date compatible with the recertification cycle;
- the name, address and symbol of the certification body itself (other symbols (e.g. accreditation symbol) may be used provided they are not misleading or ambiguous);
- data on the difference between the revised certification documents and obsolete documents. [1].

To avoid misleading third parties, information regarding references to certification results and the use of marks is significantly detailed. So, now the certification body is obliged to carefully formulate the conditions for handling the mark of conformity, which it allows certified clients to use. In particular, the conditions for applying this mark to products or packaging.

The certification body must now require that the client organization:

- complied in all details with the requirements of the certification body when references to certification results are made in the communication environment (Internet, documentation, etc.);
- did not allow any statements that could be misleading regarding the results of certification;

- did not use or allow the use of the certification documents or any parts thereof in a manner that could be misleading;
- after the suspension or cancellation of the certification results, ceased to use any promotional material relating to the certification results;
- made appropriate adjustments to the advertising material, if the scope of certification was reduced;
- has not used certification results in a way that could bring the certification body and/or certification system into disrepute and lead to a loss of public confidence.

- The clause on confidentiality, which was present in Guidelines 62 and 66, is retained in the standard, but in a significantly more specific form (diagram above).

As before, the certification body must take measures to maintain the confidentiality of information obtained during certification by all its participants acting on behalf of the certification body (only now it is also necessary to establish a confidentiality policy). [2].

An important place for the implementation of the principle of openness is the exchange of information between the certification body and its clients. Thus, the certification body must provide customers with:

- a detailed description of the certification procedures themselves, including filing an application, conducting primary audits and inspection actions, any actions to change (addition, expand, narrow) the scope of certification, as well as recertification;

- documents describing the rights and obligations of certified clients, including requirements regarding references to certification in communication tools of any kind.

Thus, it is assumed that the certified client will inform the certification body without any delay about the ability of the certified management system to continue to comply with the requirements of the standard (for example, in relation to changes regarding the legal, commercial or organizational status of the client), and the certification body for its part provide legal measures to enable the certified management system to perform its functions. [3].

Process Requirements

Unlike Guidelines 62 and 66, the standard establishes two stages of the initial audit, inspection audits in the first and second years, as well as a recertification audit in the third year of the certification period. The three-year certification cycle begins with a decision to certify or recertify.

Like Guides 62 and 66, the standard stipulates that the audit plan and timing must be agreed with the client in a timely manner.

Primary audit and certification. The certification body must require the authorized representative of the applicant organization to provide the necessary information to enable it to establish, in particular:

- general information about the organization, including its name and address, location, significant aspects of its activities, any relevant legal obligations, general information about human and technical resources, functions and internal relations, if it is a large organization;

- information on the management system consulting that has been carried out.

Before conducting an audit, the certification body shall evaluate the application and any additional information to ensure that:

- information about the organization and its management system is sufficient for the audit;

- certification requirements are clearly defined, documented and communicated to the applicant's organization. As in Guideline 66, the primary certification audit of the management system should be carried out in two stages (Table 3), however, their regulation, according to the standard, is more detailed.

The procedures for inspection control and re-assessment (re-assessment) in Guidelines 62 and 66 were practically not regulated: it was only necessary to ensure their compliance with the initial assessment procedures. The standard reflects the specifics of both inspection activities and certification for a new period. [4].

Table 3. Contents of the two stages of the initial certification audit

Stage 1 (clause 9.2.3.1)	Stage 2 (clause 9.2.3.1)
<p>performing an audit of the documentation of the management system being certified; assessment of client locations and conditions and discussion with client personnel to determine readiness for stage 2; analysis of the status of the client and understanding of the requirements of the standard, in particular regarding the identification of key parameters or significant aspects, processes, goals of the management system; collection of necessary information regarding the scope of the management system being certified, the processes and locations of the client, the relationship of legislative and other regulatory aspects with ensuring compliance (for example, qualitative, environmental, legal aspects of the client's actions, associated risks); analysis of resource allocation for stage 2 and agreement with the client on the details of stage 2; provide a focus for stage 2 planning by obtaining sufficient understanding of the client's management system in the context of possible material aspects; assessment of the situation, if internal audits and management reviews are planned and carried out so that the</p>	<p>The purpose is to evaluate the implementation of the client's management system, including its effectiveness. It must be carried out at the client's premises and include at least the following issues and objects: data and evidence of compliance with all requirements of the applicable management system standard or other regulatory document; the effectiveness of monitoring, measurement, reporting and analytical reviews regarding the fulfillment of the requirements of the applicable standard or other regulatory document for the management system being certified; the organization's management system and its effectiveness in relation to compliance with legal requirements; operational control of processes by the client; internal audit and management review; responsibility of management for fulfilling the requirements of the informed policy of the client; links between regulatory requirements, policies, objectives and performance indicators (consistent with the requirements of the applicable management system</p>

level of performance of the management system as a whole proves that the client is ready to perform stage 2. For most management systems, it is recommended that at least part of the Stage 1 activities be performed at the client's premises. Stage 1 results shall be documented and communicated to the client, including the identification of any area that could be classified as a stage 2 nonconformity.	standard or other normative document), any applicable legal requirements, personnel responsibilities and competencies, actions, procedures, performance data, results and conclusions of internal audits.
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inspection activities. The certification body shall organize its inspection activities so that representative areas and functions covered by the management system are reviewed on a regular basis and taking into account changes that have occurred in the certified management system. [5].

Inspection activities should include on-site audits and may also include requests from the certification body to the client: for example, on certain aspects of certification, evaluation of certain client actions (on the content of advertising materials, Internet sites, etc.), requests for the provision of documents and records (on paper or electronic media). Surveillance audits (on-site audits) should be carried out:

impartially and with the intent to show that the certified management system continues to meet the requirements for it in the periods between recertification audits;

at least once a year. The date of the first surveillance audit after primary certification should not be earlier than 12 months after the day of completion of the 2nd stage of the audit.

The purpose is to confirm the ability of the management system to effectively perform its functions during the entire period between audits, as well as the applicability of this system for the certification area (clause 9.4). Therefore, this audit should cover the operation of the management system for the entire certification period and take into account the results of previous surveillance audit reports. [6].

The recertification audit must demonstrate:

- the ability of the management system within the scope of certification to perform its functions effectively and for a long time in the face of internal and external changes;

— feasibility of commitments to maintain the effectiveness and improvement of the management system;

- the answer to the question whether the certified management system contributes to the achievement of the organization's objectives.

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The certification body must make a decision to renew certification based on the results of the recertification audit, as well as taking into account the complaints received and the results of the management system for the entire certification period.

Special audits. This is a new item, it was not in Guidelines 62 and 66. The certification body, in response to a request to expand the previously declared scope of certification, should analyze this request and determine the audit actions necessary to resolve this issue. Such an audit may be carried out in conjunction with a surveillance audit.

Another example is an at short-notice audit, which may be necessary to investigate a complaint or in response to changes (see above). In such cases, the certification body shall:

- inform certified clients in advance about the conditions for conducting such an audit;

- pay special attention to the appointment of an audit team, given the lack of opportunities for the organization to object to the composition of this team.

Suspension, cancellation or reduction of the scope of certification. As before, the certification body must document procedures (and now also formulate and implement a policy) for suspending, withdrawing or reducing the scope of certification and determine its subsequent actions in these cases. Unlike Guidelines 62 and 66, the standard lists cases in which it must suspend certification:

— the client's management system fails to consistently or seriously meet the certification requirements, including management system effectiveness requirements;

- the client does not allow inspection activities or recertification audits to be performed at the required frequency, or the client voluntarily requests a suspension. [7].

The standard now clearly states that failure by the client to address the issues that led to the suspension of the certificate should result in the cancellation or reduction of the scope of certification (in most cases, the suspension period should not exceed 6 months). In this case, the certification body must reduce the scope of the client's certification:

- if the excluded parts of this area do not meet the new requirements, or
- if the customer fails to meet the certification requirements for excluded parts.

Appeals (appeals). In this part, the norms of Guidelines 62 and 66 are significantly expanded in order to ensure the principle of openness of the certification body. Along with the fact that the processes of receiving, evaluating and making decisions on appeals (appeals) must be documented (clause 9.7), their description must be publicly available.

These processes should not result in any discriminatory actions against the subjects of appeal (appeal). The certification body is obliged:

- confirm receipt of the appeal and provide the appellant with reporting materials on the progress of the proceedings on the appeal and their results;
- be responsible for all decisions in the course of these proceedings, while ensuring that persons involved in the process of working on the appeal did not take part in audits or make decisions on certification (and also did not previously touch the subject of the appeal).

The process for handling applications should include at least the following steps:

- development of a scheme of processes for receiving and studying the appeal in order to decide what actions should be taken in response, taking into account the results of past similar appeals;
- tracking and registration of applications, including all actions taken to resolve them;
- ensuring guaranteed corrections and corrective actions.

Complaints. As before, the certification body should have a documented process for receiving, evaluating and resolving complaints. At the same time, confidentiality requirements must be observed, as it concerns the submitter and the subject of the complaint. The handling of

complaints should include the same elements as the handling of appeals (it is necessary to be guided by the requirements of ISO 10002:2004).

The description of the process of their processing should also be publicly available (clause 9.8.1). Upon receipt of a complaint, the certification body is obliged to confirm that it concerns certification activities, and it accepts it for consideration. If the complaint concerns a certified client, its verification includes an analysis of the effectiveness of the management system. Such a complaint is sent by the certification body to the client.

Whenever possible, the certification body shall acknowledge receipt of a complaint and provide the complainant with progress reports and results. As in the case of appeals, the persons involved in the processing of a complaint should not be previously implicated in the causes of the complaint. The certification body shall determine, together with the client and the complainant, the extent to which the subject matter of the complaint and its decisions may be made public.

Records about applicants and clients. In contrast to Guidelines 62 and 66, the categories and types of certified client records are now explicitly spelled out in the standard. As before, the certification body keeps records of customers under conditions that guarantee the observance of the principle of confidentiality of information (the standard adds that these conditions must also be observed when transporting, sending or transmitting data in any other way).

RECORDS MUST BE MAINTAINED FOR THE CURRENT CYCLE PLUS ONE FULL CERTIFICATION CYCLE.

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